

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Case Study

IRAQ

Drivers and Trajectories of Migration to Europe

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

KR-I Kurdistan Iraqi Region

PKK Kurdistan Workers' Party

IFAD International Fund for Agricultural Development

IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

JCC Joint Crisis Coordination Centre

IOM International Organisation for Migration

UN United Nations

UNHCR The office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

EU European Union

USAID US Agency for International Development

WP World Bank

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About the project “FUME”

The Horizon 2020 project “Future migration scenarios for Europe” (FUME) focuses on understanding the patterns, motivations and modalities of migration at multiple geographical scales, from international through regional to the local level, and on imagining possible futures scenarios of migration to Europe. Understanding the drivers of migration, and people’s motivation to migrate is a precondition for making projections of future migration patterns.

The analysis focuses on the examination of the demographic trends in the countries of origin and destination, migration propensity, livelihood opportunities, the demand for and supply of labour market, as well as environmental challenges that may shape future migrant movement patterns in Europe. Thus, FUME supports planning and policy-making processes at many levels by formulating integrated and coherent visions of how migration to and within Europe might evolve. The project develops the mid-term (by 2030) scenarios and long-term (by 2050) scenarios on migration to the EU by using official data from statistical offices, conducting qualitative interviews in sending and receiving locations, by using social media platforms used by migrants and an open-source scenario-based simulation tool.

Local circumstances play a major role in the migration process, from the decision to migrate through the transit process up to the settlement in the destination countries. Nearly all international migrants generally move to the largest cities in destination countries, either directly, or after one or more internal moves. This is also the case across Europe, where population growth in many cities can be largely attributed to an influx of migrants. At the same time, in countries of origin the largest cities often function as gateways to destinations abroad. Many potential migrants in villages and small towns in origin countries first move to these larger cities before leaving their country. Cities, therefore, both in countries of origin and destination, are significant determinants of global migration and small-scale local knowledge on migration is necessary to avoid misleading results associated with the limitations arising from the use of global or national patterns only.

Consequently, a major aspect of the scope and approach of the Future Migration Scenarios for Europe project is to look at specific case areas, combined with an overall analysis of migration patterns within and between these, to create scenarios for how migration may evolve in Europe. In this perspective, the project analyses differences between *low-skilled* and *high-skilled* migration, as well as the *gender* dimension and age of migration. The study develops its analysis in a broad frame of main drivers of migration: geopolitical (e.g. global legal environment, quality of governance, political stability, rule of law), environmental (e.g. temperatures, flooding, cyclones, droughts, yield crop), socio-cultural and economic (e.g. income, employment, segregation and inequality, societal openness, and demographic (e.g. population change, ageing, educational attainment, urbanization). This approach provides a deeper understanding of how migration processes work and how particular factors interact to influence the decision to migrate or to stay.

The project explores a set of regional migration and population scenarios for four European cities: Copenhagen (Northern-European capital with large Middle-Eastern migrant communities); Amsterdam (Western-European city with centuries of immigration history); Rome (Southern-European capital with large Eastern-European and Asian migrant communities); Cracow (Eastern-European city with a recent inflow of East-European migrants from non-EU countries). Also, in

countries of origin, the largest cities often function as gateways to destinations abroad. Many potential migrants in villages and small towns in the first move to these larger cities before leaving their country. In particular, the project explores the following research field: Ukraine (a new origin country of immigration to EU from Eastern Europe), Tunisia (a migration transit country with a long tradition of migration to EU countries.), Senegal (one of the main Sub-Saharan origin country of migration), and Iraq (a Middle East origin country).

In these local case studies the project investigates socio-cultural (gender and generational factors, transnational relations, role of professionals, ethnic or religious networks) and economic factors (e.g., income, unemployment rates, housing prices), political factors (e.g., security, type of political regime, potential suppression of minorities), environmental factors (e.g., threats to the livelihood of families because of environmental change or scarce resources, conflict as a consequence of scarce resources), as well as individual and collective factors (e.g., personal and family motivations to migrate, relationships in potential transit countries and countries of destination).

Executive summary/abstract

The recent development in migration research tends to highlight the necessity of going beyond the traditional theoretical framework for understanding why people migrate at the given point in time. The push and pull framework despite its relevance is limited for understanding migrations decision making and process. Instead, the FUME (Future migration scenarios in Europe) project called for analysing migration as a non-linear and fragmented process whereby cities could on the one hand serve as a stepping stone for further transnational migration or on the other, become a destination for people who initially wanted to migrate internationally. It is therefore a prerequisite for understanding the present and future determinants of migration decision to understand how the complexity of the interaction between different temporalities and trajectories and lived experiences in urban areas inform and help re-evaluate migrations aspirations and projects. This research draws on qualitative interviews with experts and potential migrants in two cities in the Kurdistan Iraqi region and advocates for an understanding of migration decisions that account for socio-cultural and geographical and temporal perspectives. In other words, the changes reflect the lived experience of Iraqis, especially those of religious or ethnic minorities. Iraq's transition to a relatively stable economy has shifted the migration processes from a safety-driven phenomenon to an economic one. Regardless of the time of their arrival in the cities of Duhok and Zakho, Informants, particularly, those who stayed over 10 years, show a sense of belonging to a place, especially as their families succeed in establishing a safe and peaceful life. However, for the Government to improve work opportunities, leaving many informants shimmering a potential move to a place such as Europe, which is more perceived as an attainable dream than a concrete and realistic project.

1. Introduction and content of the report

Iraq has undergone several environmental, political, demographic, social and economic transformations since its establishment in the 1920s. The country has experienced several direct and indirect wars, periods of democratic and authoritarian governments, and a series of “boom and bust” economic cycles. Consequently, the country has undergone major political and economic changes as well as security problems.

In recent years, Iraq has faced challenges related to a growing youth population, high levels of undereducation, rapid urbanization, significant gender inequalities, and a difficult decentralization process. Iraq, and in particular, the Northern Kurdish part of the country, has experienced many displacements, starting with the regime’s persecution of Kurds since the 1970s and culminating during the Anfal attacks. Consequently, many Kurds sought refuge in neighbouring Turkey and Iran in March 1991. With the fall of the Saddam Hussein regime, the region experienced a period of rapid urbanization and economic development. Paradoxically, Northern Iraq is now home to many Syrian refugees, particularly in the Kurdistan Region, where some 248,000 Syrians have found refuge (source: UNHCR Registration Unit, Erbil Kurdistan Iraqi). While a large proportion of these refugees live in camps, the majority of these Syrian refugees have settled among local urban communities.

The general outflow and influx of migrants due to internal conflicts and wars in neighbouring countries have contributed to changing the demographic landscape of Iraq, especially the Kurdistan Iraqi region. Another part of North Caucasians and Circassians came to Iraq during the Caucasian War (1817-1864) and the Russian-Circassian War (1860s), respectively. These early migrants gradually integrated into Iraqi society, preserving their languages and cultures. Iraq also has an Armenian-born population that moved to Iran during the Ottoman Empire period and then to Iraq. Another portion of Armenians came to the country in the early twentieth century after the Armenian Genocide. Iraq has also been a host to Palestinian refugees since 1948 and by 2003 the population of Palestinian origin reached 34,000, but as they face violence and persecution, a large number of Palestinians now live in camps in the hope of obtaining asylum in other countries (Hantook 2018). In addition, Northern Iraq is home to former PKK and their families who came in the 1990s. Finally, there is a small community of Iranian refugees, who left Iran in the late 1970s and early 1980s due to regime change in 1979. Even after the fall of the Saddam Hussein regime, the country has been exposed to recurrent violent events since 2005 due to the terrorist activities of Al-Qaeda, the Islamic State and the related conflict between Sunni and Shiite groups. These latter conflicts have significantly increased the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) (3.3 million) in addition to the large number of IDPs that already existed.

Figure 1. Source: Eklund (2014: 4)

Against this background the FUME project, consider Iraq, particularly the Northern Kurdistan Region an interesting case for understanding and highlight the main drivers of local and international migration. This includes environmental, geo-political, economic and socio-cultural factors explaining in- and out-migration. The cities of Duhok and Zakho are chosen because they are the largest cities in Duhok province which is considered the trade gate between Iraq and Turkey. Additionally, the Duhok province is home to many IDPs and refugees camp especially those originating from Syria. The combine factors make these areas a strategic laboratory for understanding how internal and international are intertwined and how the decision to move abroad is influenced by the circumstances in the potential migrants' direct vicinity.

Firstly, this report analyses the discourse of migration drivers from actual and potential local and international migrants in the urban center of interest in the Northern Iraqi Kurdistan Region (Duhok And Zakho, see also Map below). Secondly, the report examines interviews with key local expert on migration topics, who are acknowledge for their knowledge of the context and history of migration in the study area. This includes academic scholars, IOM officials and local publics' servants.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. First, the objective as well as the rationale of the study is presented. This is followed by a description of the existing migration scenarios in Iraq and the available theoretical and methodological sources. This is followed by a description of the context of the analysis. This includes a comprehensive description of the environmental context as well as the demographic, socio-cultural, economic and political context. The final part of the report is devoted to the analysis of migration factors using interview material from informants, potential migrants and local migration experts and actors.

Picture: Levi Meir Clancy/Unsplash.com

2. Objectives and Justification of the Study

Understanding why people migrate is complex. The push and pull framework have been used to analyze the drivers of migration, but there is a need to go beyond the push-pull framework.

The reasons that drive people to move at a particular time are not only economic, political or environmental, but may also be rooted in the micro-socio-cultural context. Qualitative studies using in-depth interviews with informants are one of the most powerful tools to gain a deeper understanding of what motivates people to migrate. The aim of the case study in Duhok and Zakho is therefore to capture local characteristics that explain migration decisions in Iraqi Kurdistan. The combined analysis of case studies in Iraq, Tunisia, Ukraine and Senegal will then be used to create a more comprehensive understanding of migration factors in regions with different environmental, economic and political challenges.

Description of the methodology and sample

The initial methodological approach aimed at selecting interviewees with respect to socio economic variables such type employment, educational level, gender, religious belonging, time of arrival in the city etc. In practice these quotas were difficult to implement due to various reasons among which the COVID 19 pandemic. We adapted our strategy to convenient sampling while keeping track of the potential unbalanced in the profiles of our informants.

The fieldwork in Iraq for the 'Future Migration Scenarios for Europe' project was carried out in Duhok and Zakho cities and their suburbs, all located in Northern Iraq. Despite various restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the research team has managed to conduct all 30 scheduled interviews from January to March 2021, the time in which the pandemic measures were more at ease.

The interviews were conducted using a semi-structured in-depth methodology. The interviewers directed the conversation to specific topics following the guiding interview scenario. In certain cases, clarifying questions were asked in line with the interview scenario. When respondents were not inclined to extensive biographical narratives, the interviewers conducted a more formal survey following the plan and subject of the study.

The pool of potential interviewers were the graduates of the college of spatial planning at the University of Duhok. The bachelor's program at this college provides students with extensive education and training on how to conduct interviews and data collection for developmental and socio-economic research.

The students identified were also among the top graduated students who had experiences working for local government or local/international organization in relevant projects to this study. The selected interviewers were three graduates of the college of spatial planning who are well trained in data collection and surveys and have a very good command of the English language. These qualifications enabled the interviewers to conduct the interviews in a professional manner and translate the interview responses from the local language, Kurdish and Arabic, to English language. The interviews were also evaluated, and feedback were provided to the interviewees for the pilot interviews so that improvements are made in conducting the interviews.

Impression about the sample frame

Duhok and Zakho are the largest cities in Duhok province which is considered the trade gate between Iraq and Turkey. Oil imports and the service industry are the main economic powers in the region. Designated as tourism province in Kurdistan of Iraq, the service sector in Duhok province is in continuous development. Also, many public and private educational institutions are concentrated in the Duhok and Zakho cities. At the same time, heavy industry is not represented in the province's economy and the agricultural sector is immature. Thus, the structure of the sample reflects the situation on the labor market of Duhok province. Among the low-skilled workers, we were able to interview people of different professions, primarily in the field of services: taxi drivers, restaurant employees, and shop keepers. The largest professional group interviewed were the middle-level workers. In the case of Duhok province, this is justified, as people in this category serve a large segment of its economy. Among the persons interviewed were people of the following professions: teachers, data collector, salespeople etc. Among the highly qualified employees, we interviewed NGO representatives and civil servants. Thus, our convenient sampling allowed us to cover the most economically active population of Duhok province and to represent people of various backgrounds and professions as widely as possible.

Our sample included people who moved from different regions of Iraq, both remote and those bordering the Duhok Province. The study also presents people who have moved from rural areas, small towns, and large regional centers (such as Mosul and Baghdad).

In addition, people interviewed were divided into three groups, according to how many years they are in Duhok or Zakho (newcomers, longer stayers, settled migrants) to discover various reasons for migration: economic, political, and/or security. The sample also included several people who moved from Mosul to Duhok and Zakho due to ISIS war in 2014. Among the 30 respondents, 22 people have staid 10 years or more in Duhok or Zakho.

Most of our informants identified themselves as Kurds. Muslims, Christians, and Yezidis were all represented in the group of respondents. Muslims were the majority representation in the sample (18 people), followed by Christians (10 person), and Yazidis (2 people).

Strategies and reflections about choosing and finding interviewees

Finding respondents for this case study followed two strategies: identifying potential locations of migrants within Duhok and Zakho cities, and interviewers' contacts. For example, informal settlements within these two cities are often resided by people who have migrated from rural areas and have the intention of migrating abroad. Also, there are well known apartment complexes or neighborhoods in these two cities that are resided by internally displaced people (IDPs), especially from Mosul, and many of them may have the intention to migrate abroad. Residents in these locations were the main target of our survey team. The second strategy was to use the micro-network of our interviewers to recruit participants for the study. However, in order to avoid the predominance of any one social group in the sample and to achieve the maximum diversity of migration experience., we did not exactly use the snowball method in recruiting respondents.

Criteria for the selection and identification of the students

The students who have intention of migrating abroad were identified by the interviewers through their social network with their university colleagues. This task was easy in Duhok city since the three interviewers are graduates of the University of Duhok, so they have well established social ties with students and were able to identify potential informants easily.

In Zahko, two of the interviewers are from that city and live there so they used their social network with family friends and family members to identify potential informants.

Gender dimension of the informants

The gender dimension did not have a significant importance in the responses received from the study interviews. This is mainly because most of the potential immigrants of Kurdistan and Iraq are male or families head by a man. This was also shown by the responses of female informants in this study since the interviewers were able to identify and interview female informants as shown above.

Challenges during implementation of the research plan

The main challenge in the study planning and implementation was to have female and various professional groups represented in our sample of respondents. Difficulties arose with the recruitment of people with low-skilled occupations without higher education. However, these difficulties were expected since substantially more male intend to migrate compared to female mostly due to the conservative cultural norms. Also, since education is free in Iraq, most people have bachelor's degrees. Despite these difficulties, we were able to interview 11 females and 4 people from the category of low-skilled workers. It was also difficult to find unemployed people, but we could find housewives which are also considered in this category. We were able to interview 2 unemployed people and 3 housewives, hence a total of 5 unemployed people. Our field experience showed that women were more reluctant to agree to participate in the study because of cultural norms. Because of this, the sample is not fully gender-balanced and includes 19 men and 11 women.

Ethical and other challenges

In many cases, the respondents were reluctant to provide long answers which made it difficult for the study team to persuade the interviewee to give more detail. For the online interviews, in a few cases, the challenge was with poor internet connection that interrupted the interviews and drove some participants a bit impatient to continue the interview. However, the participants were overall friendly and inviting. Many of the study participants have also recommended other potential study participants to our team after the interview sessions were concluded. The interviews were conducted at various places such as the participant house, workplace, or a cafeteria, based on the time availability of the participant.

Fieldwork during the Covid-19 pandemic

The main ethical challenge the research team faced was to maintain the safety of all the participants in the research process during the peak of the Covid19 epidemic in Iraq. Most of the interviews were conducted in person as planned but the team took all necessary measures to ensure the protection of their subjects. The interviewees wore their masks and kept safe distance from the participants. A total of 8 interviews were conducted online upon the request of the participants. The team also provided the interviewees with complete information about the project and its goals. The pandemic circumstances, however, imposed some limitations in terms of the time the participants have allowed for the interview which may have influenced the quality of the material. The participants had their concern with prolonged exposure to our team members. To cope with that limitation, our team members followed up with the participants, if necessary, when further information were deemed necessary to be added to the answers of the participants. Several interviews were updated through follow up phone calls with the participants.

Picture: Levi Meir Clancy/Unsplash.com

3. The context of the analysis

Environmental conditions

Country-level environment characteristics

The environment in Iraq is under continuous pressure due to compounding factors including rapid population growth, the impact of war and conflict in the past two decades, climate change, poor land use planning, and encroachment on fragile ecosystems. The most recent serious environmental problems in Iraq range from poor water quality, soil salinity, air pollution, inadequate waste management practices, severely contaminated areas to deteriorated main ecosystems (World Bank, 2017).

The climate in Iraq varies geographically, however. Central and southern Iraq have a sub-tropical climate with mild winters and very hot summers. While northern Iraq has a Mediterranean climate, with cold winters and mild summers. Most of the country classifies as arid to semi-arid land. It rains annually on average between 300 and 1000mm with the maximum reaching 1300 mm and the minimum 100 mm (Hijmans, Cameron et al. 2005, Held and Cotter 2006, UNDP 2010). Only 27% of the land surface in the country is suitable for farming, of which only around 60% is farmed (FAO Iraq, 2019). Drought and flooding are the results of weather extremes that occur at different times of the year.

The average daily temperature is about 5°C in winter and 30°C in summer with maximum summer's temperature reaching 50°C, especially in the south (Hijmans, Cameron et al. 2005). The average temperatures are rising at around 0.5 to 0.7 degree Celsius every 10 years. With an estimated 11 % of Iraqi families depending on agriculture for their livelihood, the extreme weather conditions escalate the risks to domestic agricultural production and livelihoods, which in turn can affect migration propensity. The resulting soil erosion and desertification from these environmental conditions compromise the sustainability of agriculture in Iraq (WFP, 2019).

Regional and local-level environmental characteristics

The Iraqi Kurdistan region is a semi-autonomous region rich in oil and is characterized by a considerable level of precipitation of orographic origin (as an indication the average annual rainfall is recorded at 700 mm) (Trigo et al. 2010). Because of the high precipitation, Iraqi Kurds cultivate in the plain specific cereals such as barley, wheat. People who have agriculture as their main source of livelihood are the most susceptible to environmental change, such as drought, or erosion. However, since a relatively low percentage of the population in Iraq have agriculture as their main livelihood; the rural-urban migration due to environmental reasons is marginal compared to other reasons such as economic, social, or political reasons. For example, a study by Eklund (2012) found that among the 1206 households surveyed in rural areas of Duhok governorate, northern Iraq, and more than a thousand rural-urban migration reported, only 10 migration events were reported to be mainly due to environmental reasons (drought being the main environmental issue). In the Duhok governorate, less than 20% of the population are involved in agriculture with slightly more than half of them actually depend on agriculture as the main source of income.

Environmental challenges

Multiple Migration Drivers have been identified throughout the evolution of migration studies. These include political, economic, social, and demographic factors (see Black et al. 2011). Only recently have environmental conditions gained more attention as a potentially important driver of current and future migration. The impacts of the extreme weather conditions also vary geographically. For example, recent increase in drought frequencies in the hottest regions of central and south-western Iraq have reduced agricultural production by 25-30 % on average and contribute to desertification of arable land (WFP Iraq - North Coordination Office 2001). The lack of arable land for farmers can be a cause for rural to urban migration, especially from other rural areas to Duhok and Zakho. Water scarcity poses additional threats, as water availability in the two major Iraq Rivers, Tigris and Euphrates; continue to decline due to drought (WFP, 2019). For example, during the summer of 2018, the southern governorates experienced serious water shortages for several reasons including the construction of major dam infrastructure projects in Turkey and Iran, and an increase in drought attributed to climate change (OCHA, 2019, 2020). Lack of clean water for household usage is also a growing problem in Iraq due to polluted rivers and lakes. However, the water scarcity issues in Iraq are largely due to aging water infrastructure. There is a failure to maintain most of the existing water infrastructure since the 1990s. Moreover, with no agreement in place on sharing and distribution of river water with neighboring countries (Syria, Iran and Turkey), the risk of water shortage in Iraq is even at higher risk (OCHA, 2020). Water related issues could be in the future a major push factors for local and international migration.

Demographic situation

Iraq's population statistics for the past two decades are based on estimates rather than complete censuses. The last census conducted in Iraq was in 1997, but it did not include the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) for political reasons explained in the political context section. The last census that included all of Iraq was conducted in 1987. The Ministry of Planning announced in January 2019 that a national census would take place in late 2020 with the support of UN Population Fund (UNFPA), but the COVID-19 situation and opposition to the census process from various stakeholders had postponed the effort (Australian DFAT, 2020). Most estimates put the Iraq population between 38 and 40 million. The country's estimated annual population growth rate is around 2.8 percent, placing it in the top 20 fastest growing countries worldwide. Iraq is a young country with nearly 60 percent of the population being under the age of 25. About 70 percent of Iraqis live in urban areas, and the urbanization rate is estimated to increase by 3 percent annually. The population is heavily concentrated in the north, center, and east regions of the country. Many of the larger urban agglomerations are located along extensive parts of the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers. Baghdad is the capital of Iraq, its largest city, and is in the center of Iraq. It has a population of between 6 and 7 million. Next to it in population size are the cities of Basra in the south and Mosul in the north, with both having populations exceeding 2 million. Most of the western and southern areas of the country is desert and is sparsely populated or uninhabited (Australian DFAT, 2020). Rapid urbanization in Iraq was not only driven by economic factors such as economic development in cities and higher urban wages but also due to unusual circumstances including the Iran-Iraq war (1980–1988), the 1991 Gulf War, the UN economic sanctions, US invasion in 2003, and the crisis that followed. As shown in Figure 2, the Kurdistan region of Iraq exhibit very high rates of urbanization (over 80%) compared to the rest of Iraq because the major cities in the Kurdistan Iraqi region (KR-I) have received great numbers of Iraqis who migrated for economic reasons or because they were forced to displace from other governorates (KRSO, 2018). On average, the urban population in Iraq reached 69.7% in 2017 with an annual urbanization rate change of 2.97%. The net migration rate was estimate in 2017 at -1.2 migrants per 1000 inhabitants (KRSO, 2018).

Figure 2. Urban Population in Iraq and KRI Governorates (1977-2014). (Census and Estimates).
Source: KRSO, 2018.

Sociocultural context

Socio-cultural characteristics and social networks

Multiple Migration Drivers have been identified throughout the evolution of migration studies. These include political, economic, social, and demographic factors (see Black et al. 2011). Only recently have environmental conditions gained more attention as a potentially important driver of current and future migration. The impacts of the extreme weather conditions also vary geographically. For example, recent increase in drought frequencies in the hottest regions of central and south-western Iraq have reduced agricultural production by 25-30% oes Rivers. Baghdad is the capital of Iraq, its largest city, and is in the center of Iraq. It has a population of between 6 and 7 million. Next to it in population size are the cities of Basra in the south and Mosul in the north, with both having populations exceeding 2 million. Most of the western and southern areas of the country is desertal urbanization rate change of 2.97%. The net migration rate was estimate in 2017 at -1.2 migrants per 1000 inhabitants (KRSO, 2018).

In Iraqi culture, the family is considered the basic unit of society, unified and integral. Households in Iraq often consist of several generations living together. Iraqis, however, may refer to hundreds of people as members of their family, as the concept of family often includes other relatives in the ancestral line. For Kurdish Iraqis in the north, social organization is more community- or clan-oriented than family-oriented. Nevertheless, the family is the first group a person joins at birth. The interests of the family are expected to be above those of the individual, and loyalty and preference are given to family members (Evason, 2016). Religion is arguably second only to family in terms of loyalty and collectivism.

Islam is the official religion in Iraq. Muslims make up about 97 percent of the country's total population. Unlike most Muslim countries, Muslims in Iraq are evenly divided between the two main sects of Islam, Shia and Sunni Muslims. Shia Muslims make up 55 to 60 percent of the total population, while Sunni Muslims make up about 40 percent. The Shia population is predominantly Arab, but also includes members of other ethnic groups. The Sunni population is more ethnically diverse: 60 percent are Arabs, about 37.5 percent are Kurds, and the rest are Iraqi Turkmen. The term "Sunni" in Iraq generally refers to Sunni Arabs. The Kurdish and Turkmen populations are considered primarily an ethnic rather than a religious group (Australian DFAT, 2020). Other non-Arab ethnic minorities include the Kurds, the Shabaks, the Turkmen and the Faili Kurds. The Arab Muslims

live mainly in the southern provinces, while the northern region is home to the Kurds. In addition to these groups, there are other ethnic and religious minorities in the Iraqi population, including Assyrians, Armenians, Chaldean Catholic and Syriac Catholic, and Orthodox. The conflict between Shiites and Sunnis and the attacks on Christians by ISIS are the cause of internal displacement from other regions to KR -I.

Education

Primary education is compulsory in Iraq and public schools in Iraq are free up to university level. Based on a survey conducted by UNICEF in November 2018, 92% of children in the country are enrolled in primary school. The survey also found that more than half of children from poorer backgrounds complete their primary education. The gap widens further at secondary school, where less than a quarter of children from poorer backgrounds complete their secondary education. The lowest enrolment rates are found in the southern region of the country (UNICEF, 2018). While Iraq was once a leader in the Middle East education sector, decades of conflict, war, and economic sanctions have eroded these educational outcomes (EASO, 2020). Urban areas such Duhok and Zakho have better opportunities for education attracting families from rural areas. There is an increased in educational facilities both in public and private sector. The number of graduates from colleges and university have increased constantly, but the labour market opportunities are not the level of the offer. There is still an imbalance between a very developed public sector and a struggling private sector for creating jobs. International migration become an option for some of these graduates, not because of absolute poverty, but because they want more in life than depending on their families.

Risks and challenges

The individual rights are guaranteed in the new Iraq constitution post Saddam regime, but the reality portrays a different picture. Both Iraqi governments (the central Iraqi government and the Kurdistan Regional Government) limit the constitutional political freedoms of the population and give little tolerance to public expressions that oppose the views of these governments. Outspoken political critics can be subject to arbitrary arrest and imprisonment. The sense of nationality and belonging for Iraqi people is in decline not only due to this lack of freedom of expression but also because of the fact that Iraqi people learn at birth to work for and defend their own family, relatives and tribes (Alwan, 2019, 2020). Iraq's education system had improved post Saddam-era with new ideas of democracy, human rights brought to the texts, and a clear increase in the budget allocated for the advancement of the education sector. However, these improvements have not capitalized to the desired level. For example, the parliamentary government allocated \$150 million from 2006 to 2014 to the Ministry of Education but the funding had added little improvement to the education sector due to mismanagement and corruption. Moreover, the education sector has had little progress in Iraq because the efforts are focused more on "brick and mortar" than on the quality of education (Marr, 2018).

Economic context (National and regional profiles)

National and regional profile

The economy of Iraq is dominantly state-run and heavily reliant on the oil industry. More than 90 percent of the government revenues, and 65 percent of gross domestic product (GDP), are from the oil sector. Iraq is the world's third largest oil exporter with proven crude oil reserves ranked the fifth largest in the world. In 2020, the World Bank ranked Iraq at 172 of 190 world economies in the 'Ease of Doing Business places' index. The government is involved in most of the economic activities and little room is given to the private sector, which leaves the countries with a critical shortage of jobs in the private sector (DFAT, 2020). The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) identifies Iraq as a 'middle development country', with the country ranked 120 out of 189 countries based on the 2018 human development index. However, social indicators remain low in sectors such as education, health, and poverty. The employment rate of the active population (15 and older) remain also relatively low at 35.3 as more than a third of young people of age 15-24 are unemployed (UNDP, 2016).

Decades of war, internal conflicts, and internal displacement have contributed to the country's failure to reach an economic growth level similar to the oil-rich countries in the Middle East. These circumstances have also contributed to an economic culture that is heavily reliant on the government. More recently, the country is under a critical fiscal crisis following the dual shock of the coronavirus pandemic and the collapse in oil prices. Without a diversified economy and an autonomous and robust private sector, Iraq remains very susceptible to economic crises whenever the oil sector is distressed (UNDP, 2019; DFAT, 2020).

The combine effect of the depreciation in oil prices and the growing number of Syrian refugees imply extra economic pressure in the country, especially in the Kurdistan Region where the Syrian refugees and the internal displaced people represent approximately 23% of the population (MPC, Iraq, 2015). According to the MCP (2015), on the one hand this situation has added more pressure on the government budget, on the housing market, the education system, the public transport as well as employment opportunities. On the other hand, influx of new refugees can be beneficial for the labour market as some migrants bring new skills and know-how.

Profile of selected urban areas: Duhok, Zakho, and the Iraqi Kurdistan region

The two areas chosen for the study are the cities of Duhok and Zakho. Both located in the Duhok governorate. The Duhok governorate is located at the Western side of Iraqi Kurdistan region bordering Turkey and Syria (See Figure 3 below). The Duhok governorate is one of the three provinces of the Iraqi Kurdistan region with Erbil and Sulaymaniyah being the other two provinces. According to the Kurdistan Region Statistical office (KRSO), the population of Duhok was estimated at 1, 45 million inhabitants and 718,000 displaced people (which include refugees and internally displaced people) living on an area of about 6600 Km² (KRSO, 2014).

Figure 3. The location of Duhok (Center) and Zakho districts where the interviews were conducted.
 Source: Ibrahim F., et al. (2021). Multi Criteria Decision Analysis Technique for Solar Power Sites Selection in Duhok Governorate–Iraq.)

Picture: Levi Meir Clancy/Unsplash.com

Duhok City

The first city considered for studying the drivers of local and international migration is Duhok. As seen in the map, Duhok City is located in the Kurdistan region, northeast of Mosul at about 65 km to the Turkish border and 180 to the Syrian border. Duhok city has experienced a rapid urban expansion due to the population growth caused by the high birth rates and the influx of IDPs, refugees, and rural-urban migration. Around 5 percent of the urban areas within the city are informal settlement (Raswol, 2017). The informal settlements continued to grow after 2003 mainly due to migration from rural areas to Duhok city. The increase in rural-urban migration was mainly due to the lack of services in rural areas and the poor security.

Most of these informal settlements have been recently formalized, by the provision of legal tenure, but remains in poor conditions. That is, they lack basic infrastructure such as properly paved roads and access to water and sanitation. These areas are the main targeted ones to conduct the interviews with potential migrants.

Zakho City

The second city chosen is Zakho, which is also located within Duhok Governorate in the north-west part of Iraq, Kurdistan region. The city is around 50 km distance from Duhok City. Similar to Duhok City, Zakho has also a similar percentage, if not more, of informal settlement formed due to similar reasons. These urban areas lack access to proper infrastructure and services, and they are dominantly resided by low-income population. The location of the city, however, can be more attractive to people with migration intentions. The city is located a few kilometres from the Iraq–Turkey border which makes it a potential location for temporary residence for people attempting to migrate, especially to Europe, through Turkey.

Risks and challenges

Both the decline of global oil prices and the ISIL conflict have plummeted the Iraq economy since 2014. During this period, the Iraq government has struggled to pay the salaries of public sector employees. Government mismanagement, corruption, and unreliable oil crude exports all contributes to the continuously struggling economic situation of Iraq. The economic situation of Iraq will never stabilize unless radical steps are undertaken to reorganize and diversify the economic sector. This volatility of employment and the uncertainty related to salary payment pushes some to question whether staying in KR-I is the safer option. So When the opportunity present itself to move to places with stable economies and reliable institutions such Europe, Iraq is clearly in disadvantage for retaining worker and avoiding brain drain particularly when the reconstruction efforts require the involvement of talents.

Political context

Geopolitical dynamics, political cleavages

After thirteen years of economic sanctions imposed by the UN from 1990 to 2003 and two wars led by the US, the Iraq society was liberated from a dictator (Saddam Hussein) but with an extreme price for Iraqi people to pay. The society was left in a state of turmoil that forced a large section of Iraq's population to live below the poverty line. The situation also caused a forced brain drain, with many highly educated people such as university professors and medical doctors fleeing the country, mainly to neighboring countries, out of the fear of targeted assassinations and intimidation (Alwan, 2020; Marr, 2018).

Conflicts - Violation of human rights - ethnic/religious/political persecution and discrimination

Historically, Iraq has endured several decades of internal conflict and war, including the war with Iran (from 1980 to 1988), the Gulf War (from 1990 to 1991), and the invasion of Iraq by the United States of America (from 2003 to 2011). In between these wars, the country also experienced the UN sanction, which consisted of a financial and trade embargo imposed in August 1990 after Iraq's invasion of Kuwait and lasted until May 2003 with the fall of the Saddam Hussein regime (see also Gibson and Campbell 2011). All these wars and conflicts create unstable living conditions with the proliferation of refugee camps. In relation to the specific region of Iraqi Kurdistan, the conflict between the Iraqi regime and the Kurdish people led to several displacements after villages were destroyed in the 1970s. The second main local factor of forced migration is the Anfal attacks between 1987 and 1988 (Barwari 2013). The Anfal campaign consists of a series of military attacks (in the form of abductions, executions and chemical weapons) carried out by the regime of Saddam Hussein against the northern governorates where most Kurds live (See Figure 4) . According to Human right watch (2013), these attacks destroyed the homes and agricultural lands in about 2000 Kurdish villages. Continued threats of attacks in 1991 led to the displacement of nearly 2 million Kurds to neighboring Iran and Turkey.

Figure 4. Areas targeted by the Anfal's attacks in the Iraqi Kurdistan region

Source: Eklund (2015:30)

Risks and challenges

The security situation in Iraq is highly unstable and unsolidified but varies by location. Daesh (ISIS) remains a major threat despite its territorial defeat in December of 2017 by the Kurdish and Iraqi forces backed by the US-led coalition forces. ISIS units have continued to attack electricity and water infrastructure and abduct and kill civilians and attack security forces mostly in Anbar, Baghdad, Diyala, Kirkuk, Nineveh and Salah al-Din Governorates. The group is believed to have joined its forces to take the advantage of ungoverned spaces and the disputed areas between the central Iraqi government and the autonomous region of Kurdistan. To add to the problem, the US-led coalition has temporarily suspended their campaign against ISIS in January 2020 to shift the attention to protecting their troops from Iran-backed militias. The group aims to exploit the confrontation between the US and Iran by attempting more complex attacks against security forces and vital energy infrastructure in central and northern Iraq (DFAT, 2020).

Migration policies on internal and international mobility to EU

The Iraqi government have made some improvement in terms of controlling irregular migration through advanced training on border security and detection of fraudulent travel documents. By reinforcing border security. The government aim also at combating Human trafficking, with the guidance of the Central Committee from several ministries. Despite these efforts, there is still lot to be done in relation to the protection of migrants in transit or at the border. There is still a clear lack of policies and procedures to oversee the rights of migrants in transit or at the border. Regarding migrant's wellbeing and rights, there are legislation in place which aim at dissuading force labour. Employers could for instance force migrants to work by confiscating their residence and work permits. The new legislation allows migrants to keep their residence and work permit even when they change employer. Despite these efforts, the immigration policy does not entail potentials effect of emigrants, especially refugees from Syria, on domestic labour markets.

In general, and depending on their residence status, migrants have similar access to public health care as natives. This is also the case for access to primary and secondary public schools as well as social protection. The management of IDPs is a huge burden for the government, especially for the KR-I government. The increasing number of IDPs and refugees from other regions of Iraq and Syria exert additional pressure on the infrastructure, the educational system, the housing system and the labour market, in the form of wage dumping. Refugees and other IDPs are often willing to work at a lower pay than Iraqi nationals.

The Iraqi government is actively involved in regional cooperation such as the Arab Regional Consultative Process on Migration and Refugees Affairs, which aim at addressing diaspora role in the country development. There also agreement with countries like Sri-Lanka allowing Sri-Lankan national to legally work in Iraq. The most proactive migration policy is the effort from the government to seek Germany's collaboration to facilitate the return of Iraqi whose asylum applications were rejected. There is also a clear policy of brain return, where highly talented Iraqi who have fled the country are encouraged to return.

Picture: Levi Meir Clancy/Unsplash.com

4. Results

Informants' characteristics

The drivers of migration are often shaped by customary rules based, for example, on pre-existing gender rules. We interviewed 30 potential migrants, including respondents of different ethnic groups, ages, education, and work experience. The respondents included 8 students, 4 housewives and 2 unemployed, while the remaining respondents were employed in different private or public sectors. Although it was more difficult to recruit female informants and female migration is often associated with migration of the head of household (mostly men), our local research team managed to include another sample of women to get a different perspective on the reasons for migration. Female informants make up about 36.3% of our total sample (which is about 11 women, see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Distribution of informants by gender

Source: Own work.

The age of the respondents ranged from 19 to 75 years. Most of them were young men who are 29 years old or younger (22 respondents), and only three respondents were 60 years old or older (see Figure 6). Our respondents are economically active, so on the one hand it was important to include their experiences of migration in the study, but on the other hand it introduces bias that we included only a few unemployed people. In addition, older residents in Zakho and Duhok have on average less desire to migrate internationally than their younger counterparts.

Figure 6. Distribution of informants by age.
Source: Own work.

Iraqi Kurdistan is the largest and most independent region for Kurds in the entire world. All of the informants interviewed self-identify as Kurds but differ in terms of the religion they practice. The largest part of our sample identifies as Kurdish Muslims (18 informants), while the number of Christians is 9 (see Figure 7). The smallest group is Kurdish Yazidis (3), who also face persecution, especially those who originate from Nineveh Governorate. In general, internal displacement due to attacks on Kurds in Baghdad and other regions of Iraq has led to the Iraqi Kurdish areas becoming a refuge for all Kurds.

Figure 7. Distribution of informants by religion.
Source: Own work.

The aim of this study was to examine the migration of drivers, taking into account the different temporalities of migration. Migrants who have spent more than 10 years in the city may have different migration triggers than newcomers. In this regard, the Iraqi sample includes 2 migrants who have spent less than 5 years in the current place of residence, 7 migrants who have spent between 5 and 9 years in Zakho and Duhok, and most informants (21 out of 30 are settled migrants, which means they have spent 10 years or more in the place of interview (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Distribution of informants by duration in the city

Source: Own work.

Who moves? Pre-migration characteristics of our informants

Economic conditions and work opportunities at origin

Iraq has experienced civil unrest and war in recent decades. Consequently, economic conditions and opportunities in the region of origin are described as relatively good but suddenly deteriorated due to conflict and attacks, especially for Kurdish informants who come from outside the Iraqi Kurdistan region such as Baghdad and Mosul. The following two informants who left Mosul and Baghdad, respectively, for Duhok and Zakho in 2014, indicate that:

"There were a lot of job opportunities. People were able to find jobs before ISIS came. Everyone had jobs. But after 2014, the situation in Kurdistan and all of Iraq worsened. Job opportunities no longer existed."

"My region of origin which was my place of birth was Baghdad (New Baghdad-Mashtal). I Lived with my husband and his mother, she was an old woman back when we were living there. We had a house and toys store there after my husband quieted his job as mechanic; we had a stable life till the war started in 2003 and we decided to go to Syria in 2003/3/12 before the US army attack in 2003/3/19. After three months living in Syria, we spent all the money we had then we came back to Baghdad. I lived 2003,2004,2005 and 2006 till I decided to move to Zakho looking for a better life."

"Agricultural and trading employment predominated, as well as manual labor such as repairing projects. And there are other additional job alternatives for underprivileged individuals in Mosul, allowing them to live well."

As these narratives shows, the economic conditions, especially in Mosul and Baghdad from are described as relatively stable. The war has had a disruptive effect in many Kurds livelihoods forcing many to leave everything behind and attempt to build another life elsewhere. Conversely, when informants originate from rural areas (such as the following informant who came from the Gersheen village), the pre-migration economic conditions are often referred to as poor, especially for young students or graduates:

"Before coming to Zakho there was the Kurdistan economic crisis and wages didn't get delivered for months. We had instability overall. But now, we can say that the situation is a bit getting improved and stabilizing. It wasn't good before but better now. Now we have more access to services and opportunities as opposite to when we were living in the villages where there weren't many services and having transportation problems. I had transport issues when moving from the village to the university and often I had to wait for 1 house till I can find a taxi."

There are cases where informants described pre-migration economic conditions as not ideal because of ethnic discrimination in the labour market. The following informants originates from Mosul and he suggest that there were already obstacles for Kurds to find a job in Mosul even before the series of attacks.

"Yes difficult. Especially after 2003, many places weren't hiring Kurds. Kurds were always receiving death threats and so, job owners did not want to risk the threat affecting their workplaces as well."

The informant's narratives are not surprising as they characterize an overall lack of economic prospects with a high unemployment rate. According to UNDP (2018), the national unemployment rate in 2018 was 11% and youth unemployment was 27% for women and 17% for men.

Educational and training opportunities at origin

When ask about the educational and training opportunities in the region of origin, the response differ in relation to the origin. For migrants who left urban center such as Mosul and Baghdad or even places like Shingal in the Nineveh governorate, the offer in education and training was relatively comparable to that of Duhok.

"Like any student, I began my education at age of 6. Essentially, I reached the 12th grade. I studied in Shingal. Then we were displaced to Kurdistan and I continued my studies in Duhok."

However, when the migrants are from rural areas, they describe the educational conditions of the region of origin as below what you can obtain in cities:

"There are no more than 2 schools in our origin place compared to the city. Good or bad you have to take it."

Environment conditions

In describing pre-migration origin characteristics, one cannot ignore the environment. Environmental conditions which include event such as natural disasters, droughts or floods may trigger the decision to leave a particular place of residence. Therefore, these factors can affect the economic conditions of potential migrants in terms of lack of resources and income or arable land. Northern Iraq, including Duhok Governorate, was affected by an acute drought between 2007 and 2009. During this period, rainfall in the governorate decreased by 50%, which negatively affected vegetation conditions (Eklund, 2014). This mainly affected people who depend on rainfall for their agriculture, while they failed to diversify their sources of income. Nevertheless, our respondents rarely mentioned the environment as a major problem in their place of residence or in their region of origin before emigration. This is mainly because environmental causes such as drought may be the main cause, but its consequences can be understood as a reason for migration. One of the few informants who mentioned difficulties in farming did not link these problems to the drought, but stated that they had moved to Duhok because they were farmers and could not make a living from the income from farming due to lack of payments from the government:

"Yet we have not received the budget. The government did not pay us our money because we sold our wheat to the government silo.... But the government should buy the wheat (corn) from us and still they are not paying for years, so if there is export and the government should give the farmers their money, it would be very useful for all."

Pre-departure information on destination

The Kurdistan region of Iraq is one of the most stable and semi-autonomous regions where the Kurds enjoy a degree of security and stability. Despite the bombing of Kurdish villages in Iraqi Kurdistan (van Etten et al. 2008) such as the Anfal and Arabization campaign of Zawita in Duhok district (Black 1993; Mansor et al. 2013). The major cities of Duhok (including Zakho), Erbil, and Sulimaniya are relatively safe for Kurds, especially those from Mosul and Baghdad, where they are more persecuted. Most informants knew about the cities of destination either through their families, their social network or through previous visits:

"We constantly came to Duhok before, so we had a lot of information about it. Duhok is very near to Mosul. We usually had visits to Duhok as a family and so we had information about it."

After these visits, all they know was that Duhok and Zakho will provide both economic opportunities and security for them and their families in case of trouble. At local level, it does not require a lot of research to know that the only Kurdish region in Iraq is a safer place for them in case of persecution. Another way pre-migration information is acquired is through relatives who did already make the trip: "Yes, so many. For example, about 40 of our relative households migrated from Baghdad" (IQMigSM10, male 38, 15 years in Duhok, Kurdish muslim, Taxi driver).

It is important to keep in mind that currently there was not a social media presence as with migration now. The relatives were a valuable source of informal information in a situation of emergency.

Migration decisions have been influenced by economic theories such as neoclassical theory, which states that the decision to migrate follows a cost-benefits calculations (Borjas 1989, Castles and Miller 2009). However, there is a growing consensus that migration decisions and drivers are too complex and often result from a combination of factors (Black, Kniveton and Schmidt-Verkerk 2011). The most commonly cited reasons in the literature are economic (jobs), security (conflict, ethno-religious persecution) and, more recently, environmental change. The increasing process of globalization and advances in transportation and communication technology since the early 1990s have reduced travel time between places. This process has encouraged the concentration of people, finance and jobs in major cities.

Against this background, cities in countries of origin become an important component of the migration process, as they can serve as a transition point for further local and international migration, but also as a destination, even though they were not originally intended as a destination. To understand future migration scenarios to Europe, we also need to capture the many facets of migration factors and the non-linear temporality of migration trajectories. In the Iraqi case study, the city of Duhok and Zakho in the Duhok governorate of KR-I provide interesting insights into these local mobility dynamics that influence transnational mobility. To capture the complexity and different temporal trajectories of migratory movements, we interviewed people who have lived in these two cities for a relatively short time (newcomers, less than 5 years in the city) or for a long time (long-term residents (5-9 years) and settled (10 years or more).

Reasons for leaving the origin

Our informants typically travel in two directions. On the one hand, we have a group that comes from other rural areas in Duhok governorate, and informants who have left other governorates, such as those who left Baghdad and Mosul to move to Iraqi Kurdistan.

Our analysis revealed that the drivers of local migration varies with the type of migrants as well as their origin and their time of arrival in the city.

Economic opportunities, a recent driver of the internal migration within the KR-I

According to interviews with our key informants, economic migration has become the most important factor in recent years. Without neglecting security issues, moving to seek work has become one of the most important drivers of internal migration in recent years. One of expert with large expertise on IDPs working for various international NGO's described the situation as follows when asked if she thought the profile of migrants in Duhok and Zakho had changed in recent years:

"...I think the change now is basically economic migration. People here just do not have work and it's not getting any better, the South is marginally better than Kurdistan, but it's fragile as we've said.... A lot of things could be undone, and the government has not really done everything it could to keep Kurdistan more stable and to provide more jobs. They did not really fulfill their mandate, I don't think."

These results confirm previous studies conducted in this region. For example, Ecklund's (2015:11) findings suggest that economic reasons account for most of the motivation to migrate in KR -I. Of the 355 households, about 40% move for economic reasons (see Figure 9). These include work and housing opportunities.

Figure 9. Reasons for migrating in Iraqi Kurdistan.

Source: Ecklund and Pilesjö (2012:52) based on a survey data.

Family and marriage migration were cited as the second determinant of migration within KR-I, which is also not surprising given the importance of family in Kurdish Iraqi culture. Most of the informants are under the age of 30 and have stated that they will move to Zakho and Duhok with their families. The reason why demographic factors are not so prominent in the discourse of our informants is most likely because demographic factors are mediated by economic and political determinants (de Haas, 2010). Moreover, these two determinants, security and attacks, are sometimes the cause of economic migration within KR -I, especially in the case of isolated villages. A prime example of this is the series of arson and military attacks on Zawita in Duhok district. These attacks have affected biodiversity and reduced the availability of arable land, in turn causing some farming families to move to places like Duhok.

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Political and Sectarian violence as a historical driver

The two successive Gulf wars, the Anfal genocide, the overthrow of Saddam in 2003, and the recent Daesh invasion have contributed to the political and social unrest in Iraq. One of the most important factors has been and continues to be religious persecution. As this expert describes the situation:

"As the West is basically used Iraq as a battle ground, whether it was the first Gulf War, or any of the others. Christians, of course, have been displaced, even though they're not actually part of the West campaigns they're very often seen as you know, allies of the West and there are just fewer, I think, since the second Gulf War I read somewhere that there are fewer Christians in Iraq and Kurdistan now than there have been for over a millennium, I mean it's quite a considerable period. And, of course, the most recent religion to really be targeted was Yezidis by Daesh. Of course, that has led to a fairly heavy migration to Germany, to America, to Australia. So, religion has played one part in, it's obviously not the only one."

These reflections are shared by another expert who was at the time of the interview working for one of the largest international non-governmental organizations:

"(...). For the internal migration, the main reason is security, and as we noticed, especially since 2014, ISIS came, and many people were displaced from their place of origin and they came to Kurdistan. Currently, we have many IDPs, but we can say most of them return, but still, we have a big number in KR-I. Until now the security is the main reason and those who cannot return is because of the security. Then it comes to the economy, their livelihood, and now, this [security] is the main challenge because they are not safe and don't feel safe to go back."

JCCC (2019) supports these claims and points out that ethnic and religious minorities (ERMs) account for 60% of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in KR-I. As for the Christian minority specifically, a report by the Centre for International Governance and Innovation shows that in an area like Basra, 75% of the 1200 Christian families have fled Baghdad to KR-I governorate, including Duhok, due to the threat. In the country, statistics show that only about 10% of the Christians living in the country in 1991 have remained in the country, the rest have moved to other countries, especially Europe, where almost half of Iraqi Christians have sought asylum (Adelman, 2015:174). Our informants also confirm these statements. Many have explained their reasons for moving to Zakho or Duhok by the threat of extremist groups. This is particularly true of Daesh attacks in Nineveh governorate, especially during the invasion of Mosul by ISIS in 2014. The following narratives from two of our informants support the claims about the persecution of ERMs.

"In August of 2014, Daesh (ISIS) attacked Shingal, we were forced to leave our home region, and this was the reason... We left many things there, such as our memories, friends, and native region, which altogether was psychologically difficult."

"I am Kurdish Muslim. The major reason that me and my family left the city [Baghdad] in the first place was because of ethnic persecution. They were always against Kurds having freedom and a free separate state from Iraq. This meant that life as Kurds would never improve, and we would have to make the difficult decision to leave."

"I lived with my husband and his mother, she was an old woman back when we were living there. We had a house and toys store there after my husband quieted his job as mechanic; we had a stable life till the war started in 2003 and we decided to go to Syria in 2003/3/12 before the US army attack in 2003/3/19. After three months living in Syria, we spent all the money we had then we came back to Baghdad. I lived 2003,2004,2005 and 2006 till I decided to move to Zakho looking for a better life. The factors that have influenced me to leave it was fear from dying by an explosive car or getting kidnapped or one of my family getting kidnapped to die by a bomb. Afraid If something happens to my children when they go to their schools. Other factors are economic factors and daily needs. Looking for a better life that we can enjoy spending our life in a quiet and safe place."

As for the informants moving to KR, more specifically to Duhok and Zakho, there are similarities in the reasons for migration between the settled migrants and those who stay for a long time. In other words, both groups reported moving to these two cities for security reasons. However, they differ in terms of events. For the settled migrants, the terrorist attacks of 2003 and the terrorist attacks in Baghdad and other regions after the fall of Saddam are often the main reason for moving to Duhok or Zakho. For the long-established, the 2014 ISIS attacks are the trigger that led many to flee other cities such as Mosul and Nineveh governorate and seek refuge in Duhok and Zakho.

Water scarcity as a future trigger for migration?

Beside the aforementioned drivers, our expert NGOs expert of IDPs raise concerns about growing issues which may affect migration patterns. According to one of the Key informants:

"The River over that went through Kalar is basically already been turned off. Iran only allows a certain amount of water, so they can no longer fish there. There's going to be major problems over there, they can no longer irrigate regularly, and I forgot whether it's the greater or lesser Zab, but even the Tigris and basically anything that originates in Turkey, we saw this last summer, of course, in Rojava, where Erdogan turned off the water and people were dying in the summer for lack of water, and so he's perfectly happy to kill as many Kurds as you possibly can there and here by turning off water. He does not care and there does not seem to be any international pressure to devise commissions similar to say the Nile river basin condition that has nine different countries looking at how to equitably distribute water. I doubt either Turkey or Iran would be willing to participate, but Iran has already turned it off and I'm sure Turkey will as well, it's not long incoming..."

She continues:

"I'm not sure it has yet, other than perhaps the destruction of this year wetlands by Saddam. But I don't think yet in Kurdistan, or in Iraq. it's likely to be so in the future, because obviously both Turkey and Iran are shutting off rivers. There was an excellent piece in Rudaw, I have to state right up front, but I know the author she's a young Canadian journalist, but it's excellent piece, more or less on water, and how water is going to be a huge issue as Turkey and Iran shut off rivers and so forth. You and I have talked about this a bit before, the complete and total waste of water in most of Kurdistan. From depletion of groundwater sources and the paving over of cities so that surface water is basically just being sent to rivers and is not being held here it's going to become an issue."

Such an assertion anticipates future problems related to water scarcity based on present-day observations, but these problems can be overlooked because, despite the growing awareness of environmental changes.

Mechanism of migration

Migration requires several elements that facilitate the move by reducing the cost of migration. Factors that help reduce the cost of migration include access to information about the destination country, networks at the destination that can help in finding housing and job opportunities upon arrival. In this case, we want to explore how pre-departure information and migrants enable such a network at destination that shapes migration decisions and patterns. Information about Duhok or Zakho was acquired in families born in KR -I or through previous visits, and the family network.

"Well, we constantly came to Duhok before, so we had a lot of Information about it. Duhok is very near to Mosul. We usually had visits to Duhok as a family and so we had information about it."

At a local level, the decision of individuals and households to emigrate is the result of a complex process shaped by the socio-cultural context of the individual and the family, and by the sense of belonging to a particular social group. This informant mentioned visits to relatives prior to migrating. By merely visiting, emotional attachment can occur with a certain place. When this is the case, the decision to leave the origin region may be motivated by fear of persecution or economic hardship. However, the choice of destination does not necessarily follow the logic of choosing the place with the best opportunities. In some cultures, the sense of belonging trumps the potential economic benefits as the main reason for migration. According to Mosa, (2016:96), "Kurdish people have tended to migrate to areas where they feel the sense of belonging, more than areas with better opportunities. For example, Bahdni people tend to migrate to Duhok and Zakho cities, instead of Erbil and Sulimaniya where job opportunities are higher, because the dialect and the life style are different in the latter from what they are used to. Similar reasons apply to Sorani s as they prefer to move to Erbil and Sulimaniya more than Duhok city".

At an international level, the desire to move to Europe is shaped by how Europe is perceived in the minds of potential migrants. These opinions about Europe are not formed through formal channels and research, but through informal networks of friends or family members who either live in Europe or have returned:

"Yes, my friends have always encouraged me to leave the country because they have greater employment options now that they have automobiles and nice jobs. They also tell me that if I move to Germany, there will be a lot more work prospect. Furthermore, they tell me that if I come to Germany, we will assist as much as we can."

This informant is a young Kurdish Muslim of 25 who moved to Zakho 14 years ago with his parents from a village near Zakho. He is trained as an accountant and is currently unemployed. She claims to have been encouraged to flee the country by friends living in Europe. This indicates the influence of informal channel for acquiring information about Europe.

Reasons for choosing the destination

Local migration within KR -I, meaning people leaving other (often rural) areas to move to Duhok and Zakho are attracted primarily by the prospect of improving their circumstances, as urban life offers economic and educational opportunities offered by the urban life, which support urbanization theory. Following the reconstruction after the fall of Saddam Hussein, the KR -I gain in stability and autonomy. Oil revenues transferred to the Kurdistan Regional Government from the Iraqi state have provided the region with the necessary funds to initiate policies aimed at increasing foreign investment, particularly investment in urbanization, higher education and luxury hotels (see Gunter 2012). This has participated in the development of Duhok and other urban centers as the main attraction point for potential local migrants or IDPS looking for jobs, education and training opportunities combined with security. The following informants highlights this in the following:

"Well, in terms of job and living opportunities, I can say that they are the same. Duhok has been developing vastly in that area for years, and the people here are quite friendly, not to mention the vast security spreading across the region and the beautiful environment. For me personally, Duhok city, if given the job opportunities return to what they used to be about 4 years ago, is so much better than Baghdad."

"There are not many services here, no health centers, nothing. There are schools, but only some teachers work in them. There are no job opportunities here and you have to go either to Duhok or somewhere else to find a job."

In this case study, the quality of education seems to be an important motive for migration due to the sample bias. A large proportion of the sample consists of young men who are 29 years old or younger (n=22). As the following informants puts it with regards to the educational system in Iraq:

"The reason why the [educational system] is not good is because once you graduate, you will probably stay at home as there aren't job opportunities or government appointments. The private sector is almost non-existent. A large percentage of graduates are waiting for government appointments which has stopped over the past years. The government can no longer appoint everyone. There has to be role for the private sector similar to the developed countries so that at least 50% will be appointed and 50% to work in the private sector and not entirely relying on the government."

Research has shown that educational opportunities are an important aspect of the decision-making process, especially for families with school-age children (Tuathail and O'Loughlin, 2009; IOM, 2019) or for young men and women seeking university and training opportunities that will hopefully lead to employment.

Moving to Zakho and Duhok: an opportunity for women emancipation

In addition to the opportunities that cities offer, our informants bring the gender dimension into play by claiming that women have a greater chance of getting an education and being more independent by getting a job. Consequently, these cities could be an important space for women's emancipation. This is summarized in the following statement by some of our informants:

"The city there are more opportunities to realize your desires, to find the job you want, to get the degree you want, to live an independent life. There is a big difference between the life of a woman living in a rural area and the life of a woman living in a city. Women in cities have more opportunities to go to school, work, and be independent without people interfering in their lives."

"Well, I agree with the idea of getting better living in cities. Small communities like Chra there are lacking health services, educational services like schools and colleges, diversity and job opportunities. These were the main factors. There is something important to mention, I believe that in urban areas there is no comparison between men and women, everyone will study and go to the college they want, get the job and eventually have an independent life. In rural areas, it seems impossible for women to have their rights and live an independent life."

"There are more possibilities in the city to make your wishes come true, to find the job you want, to get the degree you want, to have an independent life."

These 3 informants are long stayers and settle migrants but what they have in common is the age category. What they seem to find important is the possibility for women to gain more independence thanks to the opportunities offered to them in terms of education and work. The life in rural areas is still heavily based on tradition where women have more restriction with regard the choices they make.

Overall, this case study of Duhok and Zakho is a specific example of the fact that the factors that make a city attractive to migrants often overlap with the push factors. Given the local context of the persecution of ERMs, particularly Kurds living outside KR -I, the attractiveness of the cities of Zakho and Duhok stems from a combination of the economic opportunities and relative security in these cities. But for the informants originating from rural areas especially in KR-I, cities offer much more than safety or security. They offer education, work possibilities, better health facilities, with women being the most affected by these opportunities.

Pre-departure expectations and current situation

The aim of the project FUME was to analyze the non-linear aspects of migration efforts, projects and aspirations. In the region of KR -I, the city where we conducted the interviews, on the one hand the server is considered a transitional station and on the other hand it can become the final place of settlement for many migrants who manage to build a stable and peaceful life. By comparing the actual perception of their current living conditions with their expectations before their departure, we aim to capture elements of their life experience that may influence the likelihood of them staying, returning or going abroad.

Picture: Andre Klimke/Unsplash.com

PreDuhok and Zakho, a safe haven for persecuted ERMes

The decision and aspiration to migrate is based on expectations shaped by the perceived image or opportunities of the destination country. Once the decision is made, the experience in the host region, city, or country can either fulfil the initial expectations or disappoint these preconceived notions. In the case of Duhok and Zakho, there is a degree of perceived stability that applies not only to these two cities, but to the KRI as a whole. In recent times, economic development has also portrayed the region as economically attractive. This makes the KRI attractive not only to Kurds from other Iraqi regions, but also to other refugees outside Iraq. We asked our informants whether their experiences in these two cities matched their pre-migration expectations. In terms of safety, the relative majority of responses appear to be positive. As the following informant puts it:

"My situation changed for the better. It was dangerous for us to stay in Anbar because of terrorism [ISIS attacks in 2014], while currently we are living peacefully in Duhok and we are able to study, and my family members can work."

"In general, positively. Our family situation improved. We feel more comfortable than we were in Baghdad. The situation in Baghdad, ever since 2003, is getting worse day by day. The security situation is not getting better. People always say that even though there are no services and utilities, but still the important thing is to have security."

In answering the question, these informants emphasize the security aspects by comparing the precarious situation in Baghdad and Anbar with the relatively stable conditions in the KRI governorate of Duhok.

Underwhelming employment prospects

Since the fall of Saddam Hussein in 2003, progress in urbanization and economic growth has been noticeable despite the economy's heavy dependence on oil revenues. Migration to Duhok and Zakho is not only related to the relative safety of these two cities KRI, but also to the potential economic opportunities, especially for those coming from rural areas, some of which have been affected by a decline in arable land due to man-made fires, droughts, or lack of sustainable income from agriculture. But how do the informants describe their current economic situation in relation to their expectation before departure. Informants have diverse experience, while some may have had positive experience, other face more disillusion. The following informants have had positive experiences in relation to the labour market.

"No, we used to face this problem before in the origin location but so far here we are living well. My brother has gotten a good job and the situation is getting better."

"We had a lot of positive points after living here as it is my birth place and we didn't face ethnicity issues with others and felt more comfortable. My husband was able to find a better job and my children had better educational and job opportunities than they did back in Mosul. Safety is crucial in stabilizing lives."

Despite this progress, there is still a lack of employment opportunities. Employment prospects do not match the rising level of education. As a result, unemployment among young graduates in these cities is critically high. This is highlighted in the discourse by both experts and informants:

"I think the change now is basically economic migration. People here just do not have work and it's not getting any better, the South is marginally better than Kurdistan, but it's fragile as we've said.....A lot of things could be undone, and the government has not really done everything it could to keep Kurdistan more stable and to provide more jobs. They did not really fulfil their mandate, I don't think."

Pressure from the arrival of refugees and the subsequent wage dumping

While the expert cites the lack of government strategy and policy to increase employment opportunities as the main cause of increased unemployment, some informants argue that the arrival of refugees from Syria and internally displaced persons in the region exert additional pressure on the labour market, especially in the cities of Zakho and Duhok.

"There are positive and negative points. If we talk about productivity, we can see that many things, that didn't exist here before, were introduced by them such as decorations, craftsmanship skills. A lot of the IDPs have skills that brought with them new types of work or example, even a negative aspect being the Nargilla. Before 2011, we would rarely see Nargilla in Kurdistan, but now, it is widely spread after the influx of people. Negative factors you can say that IDPs and refugees who came from Sinjar and Syria had a great impact on job opportunities as they were unskilled workers working in restaurants for example.

They were satisfied with less wages than local workers. I remember having some friends who went to work in a garbage treatment plant in Duhok and they were about 40 workers, all 40 of them were fired and replaced with Syrians who settled for less wages (from 500 dollars to 350 dollars).

Another negative impact is related to access to education for example when people from Sinjar first came here, they all used to study in Mosul and when they came into the region, all student graduation averages rose as the number of students increased and they took positions of local students. These are the positive and negative impacts that I can see."

"I think it has had two sides of effects. Back in 2006, it had positive effects on the region because the people who came from Mosul and Baghdad had knowledge and good craftsmanship and a lot of the teachers from Mosul university were highly educated and skilled which added a benefit to Duhok city. However, in 2014, the area suffered a lot from the influx of IDPs and refugees. We had a lot of our schools dedicated for their shelter. Many job occupations were filled with new labor and local workers were struggling as they occupied a significant share of the labor market."

These informants point out that these cities are under pressure because they are receiving too many refugees and internally displaced persons for the cities' economies to handle. They believe that the newly arrived refugees are affecting the existing population as they are willing to work at lower wages than the already resident population and long-term residents, which has drastic consequences, especially for the job prospects of local youth. So, the arrival of Syrian refugees is having an impact on wage dumping, according to our informants:

"Well, I think they had a large impact, especially in Duhok, a local employee will not be able to afford a work for less than 500\$ per month while a Syrian refugee for example will settle for 300\$ per month. This is because they don't pay any rents or taxes and they constantly received support from Humanitarian Organizations. This causes competition of labor for the local labor force and affects local people in Duhok for access to jobs."

Future migration intentions to move abroad

The methodological design of the FUME origin case study research aimed to capture the complex trajectories and constant adjustments of migration aspirations and decisions. Migrants originating from rural areas are often attracted to what urban life has to offer in terms of job opportunities, health, infrastructure, technology, education and training opportunities. In the Iraqi case study, in addition to these amenities, the cities of Duhok and Zakho provide a stable and relatively peaceful settlement for Kurds, especially those who are persecuted outside of KR -I. These cities may serve as stepping stones for international migration candidates due to their location on the Turkish and Syrian borders.

Previous research on the determinants of migration from Iraq to the European Union suggests that the decision of Iraqi nationals to migrate is due to a combination of several factors at the individual, household and community levels (Cummings et al., 2015).

Economic migration: a relatively new triggering factor

Our analysis shows that informants are likely to leave because of the relatively higher political stability and economic opportunities that Europe offers. This may indicate a new breed of economic migrants from Iraq, whereas traditional Iraqi migrants to Europe have often left because of armed conflict, ethnic or religious persecution.

"The reasons for wanting to leave Iraq was because the employment and social situation has been worsening recently and political issues are always present. We want to leave to a safer and more stable place for myself and my family."

"I am willing to leave because there is no future here to live for. Because there are almost no work options for the youth, many students graduate with no plans for the future, especially since the 2014 ISIS crises worsening the country's economy."

"If you talk about Iraq's situation, which is a non-stable country and suffers from political instability and the future is always uncertain for their people. How can I say, it is hard for people to be optimistic about this country since it needs a lot of work to reduce all this corruption and social injustice within classes? You can see poor people getting poorer and rich people getting richer and instability always exists. For a country that is willing to develop, they need to establish a governmental system that is just and willing to enhance people's lives so that people to live in welfare. I think this system is hard to develop in this country and need major changes for people to not think about migrating. So that's why, I think for those people who face challenges and have dreams of improving their lives, then migration is pretty much the only option and cannot wait for one day and hope the system in Iraq would improve and be stable."

These informants may be seeking a relatively more politically stable place to move to, but the consistent theme in their narratives is unemployment and worsening economic conditions, especially for young university graduates. The willingness to move to Europe does not vary with respect to the time of arrival in the city. New comers, long stayers and settled migrants would equally seize the opportunity if they could move to Europe. A key informant paints the economic situation the country in the following way:

"[...] because after the second Gulf War basically laying waste to Iraq's infrastructure, Saddam had many faults, but he did provide decent infrastructure, there were jobs there was you know decent electricity, water. There were postal systems, you know things like that, and as that was destroyed and has not been well replaced, we have tons of young people in Iraq, who are educated and unable to find work. I am not sure that one's as large, but it still feeds an urge for migration, going overseas to get degrees, but basically you know you get the degrees and then you need to go somewhere. Because you can't come back here and there's no work."

The analogy to the situation under Saddam is an indication of the relative severity of the economic situation which bears uncertainty about the future. Being a safe place to settle in is no longer sufficient for Duhok and Zakho and the KR-I regions. There may be strategies in place to create the necessary conditions for a long-term economic development.

On the perception of Europe as a potential destination

Despite the recent tightening of immigration policies in many European countries, Europe is idealized in the minds of potential migrants as a place where it is easy to live because of perceived general safety and good economic conditions. The words used to describe Europe are "safer", "nicer", "better jobs", "better opportunities", "quality of study", "better life". When asked what do you think of Europe? The following informant confirms that Europe is attractive as a destination for Iraqis:

"Well, I think there are some advantages and disadvantages concerning this question. The health sector is highly developed there. There is insurance on all aspects of the human life. For example, in Iraq, you will only be able to take your children to a doctor if you can afford it. Otherwise, the health services are costly for people. In Europe, your children's future is pretty much insured and safe. This was related to the health sector. But if you consider jobs, if someone has a job here in Iraq, it is much preferred than to have a job in Europe since it is very difficult to work there, and everything is accounted for. If you, for example, take a day off in Iraq it will be easier than to do so in Europe. Also, the majority of your income will be spent on taxes."

This is in line with the claims of one expert on immigration who works for a local organization providing legal advice to immigrants:

"Well, as I said, Kurds love to migrate to UK and Germany. Germany because of its good economy, but UK because of the language and then the economy. If you are going to leave and start a new life, you prefer to start a new life somewhere where you can learn the language that you might be able to use everywhere. This was in the past, however, right now, European countries that are not English speaking do teach their children from kindergarten or first grade English, so they will speak two languages. For instance, when I was in Sweden, I never faced a problem because literally everyone was speaking English, and having this will shift maybe the desire, the destination from UK and Germany to maybe closer countries like Hungary, Poland and Greece maybe. I think there will be a shift, because Europe is changing as well, to have a more united European standard for language."

Many factors play a role in choosing a destination country, such as language. Germany and English-speaking countries as well as Scandinavia (e.g. Sweden, where many people speak English) are among the preferred destination countries of some of our informants. Despite the fact that it cannot be generalized to the entire population, we ask informants where they are from and where they would like to emigrate internationally if they had the opportunity. Many informants came from Baghdad and Mosul (See size of link from Mosul and Baghdad to Duhok and Zakho in Figure 10), which confirms the claims of previous informants who declared leaving the country after the unrest in Baghdad and Mosul, where the lives of Kurds were in danger. Most migrants would prefer any European country, as shown on the figure Germany and the UK are very popular destinations for our informants (see Figure 10).

According to experts, some European countries remain popular with potential Iraqi migrants because they have relatively liberal admission policies for refugees. These statements are not based on fact, but on information from migrants who either live in Europe or have attempted to travel there.

"Talking about countries, in Europe, we are talking about Germany, we are talking about Austria, Sweden. I think those are the top in my mind. Also, the countries that are, I don't know how the procedure works, but the countries that are less strict in their approval for migrants, for example, based on my observation, people were preferring Sweden in the past. Right now, they are not preferring Sweden, they prefer Germany because Sweden is stricter, it's getting stricter, day after day, on giving the approvals for migrants. People are changing preferences; people are looking for any land that give the opportunity to live like other."

Figure 10. Origin of informants and their preferred destination for international migration. Source: Own work.

During the different phases of migration, some Iraqi respondents did not have a specific destination country but wanted to get to Europe in general. For those who had a specific destination country, the main reasons for choosing that country were an existing network of relatives and friends in that country and security-related reasons.

Deterrents to moving abroad

Although all respondents stated that if they had the opportunity they would move to Europe or another international country, almost none of the respondents had a realistic and short-term plan to move to Europe. This discrepancy between the attractiveness of Western destinations in general and the lack of concrete migration projects is indicative of the discouraging nature of legal and irregular barriers to migration. On the legal side, visa restrictions and asylum policies of European countries have a deterrent effect on migration, as the probability of obtaining a visa is low. As for illegal routes, informants hear about the multiple dangers that illegal migrants face when trying to reach Europe. The following informant explains why illegal migration is not an option for him.

"No, we have not [considered migrating internationally in the near future]. This is because I don't wish to place myself and my family in any danger of illegal migration. I would only consider safe invitation to fly to an abroad country to live and work in...The main difficulty of migrating is the way. I have heard of a lot of people who have tried to migrate but were forced to return back home once reaching countries such as Greece and Bulgaria. Also, the way is dangerous and unsafe."

With this knowledge of the unattainable dream of a destination such as Europe as a potential migration destination, informants were asked what may persuade them stay in Iraq in the future. Most respondents indicated that an improvement in living conditions, job security, and health conditions could persuade them to stay:

"If I can improve living condition, I am willing to stay in Iraq."

"If I am able to improve my working conditions and the country gets safer, then I don't need to migrate."

"If I get health insurance here the same as in Europe, then will take care of me, then I will not leave Iraq."

Our analysis shows that the decision to emigrate to Europe or abroad is rarely the result of a clear plan. This is also in line with the existing literature (Loschmann, Kuschminder, & Siegel, 2017; IOM, 2016; Schapendonk, 2012). Europe is seen as an unattainable dream due to the barriers to legal migration and most consider illegal routes too risky. When asked if they would go to Europe, most informants admitted that they would migrate to Europe if they had the opportunity. However, the obstacles to legal migration and the stories they hear about the dangers of illegal migration lead most to not even attempt to migrate to Europe.

In fact, most do not attempt to apply for a visa because the chances of obtaining one to enter Europe are slim. A temporary move to Turkey as a transition country has also been found in previous research to be a coping mechanism to increase the chances of entry to Europe.

Picture: Levi Meir Clancy/Unsplash.com

5. Conclusion

Migration in Iraqi Kurdistan, especially in the cities of Duhok and Zakho, is a complex phenomenon in which several factors interact. The most important and influential cause of migration in Iraq's recent history has been sectarian violence and persecution of ethnic and religious minorities, particularly the Kurds. Iraqi Kurdistan, with its semi-autonomous status, is one of the safer and closer options for Kurds to move there, whether fleeing unrest in Baghdad or, more recently, attacks in Mosul by ISIS.

The situation of Iraq is Unique in terms of the continuum between rural to urban migration and international migration. The rural to urban immigration is marginal in the Iraqi Kurdistan compare to other regions in Sub-Saharan Africa or the middle East.

Our analysis shows that despite the opportunities offered by these cities, many migrants who move there do not fully settle. Although some family members have managed to find work, the unemployment rate and deteriorating economic conditions limit the long-term prospects of KR-I residents, especially young graduates. This could lead to a shift in international migration from security-oriented to economic migration in the future. The linkage between internal and external migration is not linear due to the barriers to legal and irregular international migration mentioned above. Regarding the temporal component, the timing of arrival in the city is indicative of the push factor from countries of origin, with long-established migrants mentioning the attacks on Baghdad in the 2000s and long-term resident migrants mentioning the invasion of Nineveh (Mosul) in 2014 by ISIS, while new arrivals state that they moved to the city for work, education, etc. However, time spent in the city does not necessarily affect willingness to move abroad. Newly arrived refugees are just as willing to move to Europe as Iraqis suffering from economic hardship, the volatility of government salaries, and unemployment. What these different profiles have in common is that an eventual journey to Europe requires resources that are not accessible to the poorest in society. Consequently, international migration outside KR -I is not driven by absolute poverty, but by the mere fact that one can improve one's livelihood and have better future plans. The temptation to migrate abroad is compounded by a sense of hopelessness about the future of the country. There is a clear lack of confidence in the institutions that can mitigate the deterioration of economic conditions and employment opportunities.

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